

Revalidation of *Isomantis* Giglio-Tos, 1917

Kris Anderson

Giglio-Tos first established *Isomantis* in 1917 as part of his subdivisions of *Stagmomantis* into six different groupings to which he ascribed genus level status. Giglio-Tos noted that the differentiating characters of *Isomantis* include an elevated, pentagonal-shaped lower frons, an opaque costal area of the male forewings, and metathoracic basitarsi having a greater length than the remaining tarsal segments combined. Of the several *Stagmomantis* species already described prior to this action, Giglio-Tos only assigned *domingensis* to *Isomantis*. The new genera that Giglio-Tos established apart from *Stagmomantis* were soon after synonymized by Hebard in 1922, who noted in regard to *Isomantis* that “one alone of the genera so separated, *Isomantis* Giglio-Tos, appears to have validity, or to be at least worthy of subgeneric rank”.

Beier upheld the validity of *Isomantis* in 1935, listing this genus apart from *Stagmomantis* and further detailing the morphological differences between the two genera as including strongly protruding compound eyes in both sexes of *Isomantis* in combination with a straight vertex and shortened supra-anal plate. Rehn also concurred with Giglio-Tos’ findings and additionally documented the wing maculation differences between *Stagmomantis* and *Isomantis* and, more importantly, cited the unique structure of *Isomantis* genitalia. In 1935, Rehn wrote:

Of the genera split off by Giglio-Tos from the previous conception of *Stagmomantis* but one, that of *Isomantis*, based on *Mantis domingensis* of Beauvois, a species confined to certain of the Greater Antilles, is a recognizable genus, possessing as it does a combination of characters not found in the species here considered to belong to *Stagmomantis*. This opinion is in agreement with that already expressed by Hebard regarding *Isomantis*. ... In showing the relationship of *Stagmomantis* to the more closely allied genera, I would place before it the above-mentioned *Isomantis* Giglio-Tos. This Antillean genus has certain very definite and distinctive features when compared with *Stagmomantis*, such as the transverse tegminal stigma (female) or stigmal spot (male), the hyaline, non-tessellate character of a considerable part of the wings of the female, and the strongly bifid apex of the robust, instead of simple, elongate

falcate or spiniform, sinistral ventral genital valve of the male. The latter feature alone is an unusual one, in no way even suggested by any *Stagmomantis*.

In subsequent works by Beier in 1964 and 1968, *Isomantis* remained as a valid genus and was listed as endemic to the Antilles. However, in 1995, Terra disregarded all of the previous authors' findings to the contrary and listed *Isomantis* as a synonym of *Stagmomantis*. Terra noted Beier's support of *Isomantis* as a valid genus and also cited Rehn's independent conclusions of the same but neglected Hebard's input into the problem. Further, when citing his reasoning for a synonymy between *Stagmomantis* and *Isomantis*, Terra focused entirely on a single morphological character between the two genera and completely ignored the other more salient differences that were clearly documented by the previous authors, including that of genitalia uniqueness within *Isomantis*. Terra writes:

It is considered *Isomantis* Giglio-Tos synonymous with *Stagmomantis* Saussure, because the former differs from the latter only by the fact that it has a pentagonal frontal shield, which is insufficient to justify the maintenance of the genus.

As previously pointed out by Giglio-Tos, Hebard, Beier, and Rehn, the demarcation between *Stagmomantis* and *Isomantis* is not restricted only to the shape of the lower frons, which Terra seems to suggest. There are, as noted, other salient differences with the morphology of *Isomantis* pertaining to the compound eyes, vertex, basitarsi, supra-anal plate, wing maculation, and male genitalia, in addition to the geographic isolation of *Isomantis* where *Stagmomantis* does not occur.

Modern authors have not supported Terra's cursory conclusion for synonymy of these two genera. In 2007, Agudelo et al. continued to list *Isomantis* as a separate genus. Most recently, in 2019, Schwarz and Roy published a photograph of male *Isomantis* genitalia that definitively demonstrates the differences in copulatory organs between *Isomantis* and *Stagmomantis*, as first noted by Rehn many years prior. Schwarz and Roy wrote that, "some of the genera synonymized by Terra (1995) with *Stagmomantis*, like *Isomantis* Giglio-Tos, 1917 will probably have to be revalidated."

Given the historical documentation from multiple authors regarding the differentiating characters of *Isomantis* morphology in conjunction with the more modern findings of genitalia distinctions of this genus that are not shared by *Stagmomantis*, the previous synonymy put forth by Terra is hereby rejected and *Isomantis* is to be reinstated to the status of a valid genus.

Isomantis Giglio-Tos, 1917 **stat. rev.**

Description. Habitus of medium size. Significant sexual dimorphism present. Habitus of male slender and moderately elongated, that of female more stout, robust. Head capsule triangular, wider than tall. Compound eyes strongly protruding, prominent, rounded. Ocelli small in female, moderate in male. Antennae filiform, reaching to base of pronotum in male, much shorter in female. Lower frons pentagonal, nearly as high as wide, disc with longitudinal carinae. Vertex nearly straight, equal in elevation to dorsal surface of compound eyes. Pronotum slender, significantly longer than forecoxae, supracoxal dilation marked, oval. Metazona many times longer than prozona, keeled; prozonal margins converging, denticulate. Forecoxae with contiguous apical lobes on interior surface; anteroventral margin denticulate, more so in female. Forefemora slightly dilated, dorsal margin slightly sinuate to straight, tibial spur groove placed in distal half, almost in middle. Forefemora with 4 discoidal spines and 4 posteroventral spines, between which margin is smooth. Anteroventral margin with alternating large and small spines. Foretibiae with 8-9 posteroventral spines, 14-15 anteroventral spines. Meso/metathoracic legs long, exterior surface rounded. Metafemora without apical spine; basitarsi longer than other segments combined. Male forewings narrow with rounded apices, about equal in length with abdomen, parallel. Male forewings with costal area narrow, opaque, irregularly reticulated. Jugal lobe hyaline. Female forewings always shorter than abdomen, opaque, elliptical, apex broadly rounded, margins subparallel. Costal area narrow, opaque, densely reticulated. Stigma distinct, transverse, and generally bright white in both sexes. Male hindwings long and ample, maculated with radiating rows of blotches. Female hindwings primarily hyaline throughout basal portion of anal area, becoming tessellated with colored bands in distal third. Male abdomen cylindrical, ribbon-like; female abdomen broad, moderately dilated with continuous margins. Supra-anal plate very short, triangular with rounded apex, keeled, wider than long. Subgenital plate very large in male, slightly longer than wide. Cerci long, cylindrical, styli very short. This genus is endemic to Cuba and Hispaniola.

Type Species. *Mantis domingensis* Palisot, 1805 (by monotypy)

Species Checklist:

- *Isomantis domingensis* (Palisot, 1805)

References. Linné (1758) pg 426; Palisot (1805) pgs 61-62; Burmeister (1838) pgs 534; de Haan (1842) pg 75; Guérin-Méneville (1857) pg 348; Burmeister (1864) pg 237; Saussure (1871) pgs 50-52; Saussure (1872) pgs 245-247; Stal (1877) pg 39; Cockerell (1894) pg 258; Westwood (1889) pg 36; Saussure & Zehntner (1894) pg 146; Rehn (1903) pg 131; Kirby (1904) pg 254; Giglio-Tos (1917) pgs 54; Hebard (1922) pg 339; Werner (1925) pgs 160-161; Giglio-Tos (1927) pg 383; Beier (1935) pgs 95; Rehn (1935) pgs 219; Beier (1964) pg 948; Beier (1968) pg 10; Terra (1995) pgs 69-70; Agudelo et al. (2007) pg 123; Schwarz & Roy (2019) pg 161

Species Photographs. *Isomanis domingensis*: A, male dorsal habitus. B, male ventral habitus. Sierra Maestra Mnts, 30km E Marca del Portillo, Granma, CUBA, 29 Jun 2016, Anderson Collection.

Isomantis domingensis (Palisot, 1805)

Description. Habitus of moderate size, slender in males, significantly more robust in females. General coloration green or brown, with females most commonly occurring in green phase and males typically brownish with green extremities.

Head capsule. Triangular, broad, vertex nearly straight, slightly lower in elevation to dorsal surface of compound eyes. Head capsule colored same as body color. Lower frons squarish in female, spanning nearly as high as wide, with superior margin broadly arched. Lower frons more rectangular in male, spanning wider than high, with superior margin culminating in narrow plateau. Disc with two longitudinal carinae in both sexes. Compound eyes protruding, prominently swollen, rounded, pigmented same as body color, often with lateral band of yellow. Male ocelli moderate, those of female smaller but remaining conspicuous. Male antennae very elongate, setaceous, reaching to abdominal tergite III. Female antennae moniliform, reaching into distal third of metazona. Antennae dark brownish-black in both sexes, becoming greenish at base.

Pronotum elongated, measuring longer than forecoxae, variably slender in both sexes. Supracoxal dilation marked, elliptical, with distal portion of metazona gradually conforming into expansion in females, more abrupt in males. Pronotal margins minutely denticulate, more pronounced in female. Prozona margins sub-parallel, metazona margins constricted. Metazona three times longer than prozona, keeled. Coloration of pronotum typically uniformly green or brownish. Green phase individuals may have violet shading.

Prothoracic legs. Anteroventral margin of forecoxae denticulate with unequal teeth, more so in female. Posteroventral margin of forecoxae with rough texture. Exterior surface of forecoxae solid green or light brownish, occasionally with 2-3 irregular darker bands in dark phase individuals. Both sexes with base of forecoxae typically adorned with large, blackish to brownish maculation on interior surface. This blotch may be absent or faded in some individuals. Forefemora narrow, dorsal margin slightly sinuate to straight, tibial spur groove placed in distal half, almost in middle. Forefemora bear 4 posteroventral, 13-16 anteroventral, and 4 discoidal spines, all of which are black-tipped. External surface of forefemora patterned similar to forecoxae by either being solid green or brownish, with 2-3 wide, irregular darker brown bands of varying intensity in darker phased individuals. Internal surface of forefemora colored brownish-purple to green, immaculate. Foretibiae approximately half the length of forefemora, bearing 8-9 posteroventral and 14-15 anteroventral spines, all with black tips. Pigmentation same as body color, usually with darker median band in dark phase.

Meso/metathoracic legs long, slender, exterior surface rounded. Metafemora without apical spine; basitarsi longer than other segments combined. Pigmentation of meso/metathoracic legs green to brown. Base of meso/metathoracic femora commonly tinged with violet in green phase individuals. Meso/metathoracic legs usually green regardless of body color in males, often contrasting against the typical brownish body pigmentation. Green coloration of meso/metathoracic femora often transitioning to yellowish-brown toward distal apices. Tarsi concolorous with legs.

Wings. Male forewings narrow with rounded apices, about equal in length with abdomen. Anterior half of discoidal area opaque, mottled with green and brown amid white venation. Posterior portion of discoidal area entirely hyaline with scattered brownish maculation confined to individual cells. Basal third of forewing typically

traversed by oblique white crescent-shaped marking that derives from stigma. Whitish maculation occasionally faint to absent in some individuals. Additional whitish marking may occur more basally near costal ridge. Costal area weakly dilated at base then quickly narrowing, becoming almost nil past basal third, opaque, colored whitish-hyaline with darker green margin. Jugal lobe hyaline. Female forewing length highly variable with seemingly no correlation to body size. Length always measuring shorter than abdomen but may extend to tergite III-VIII. Forewings consistently opaque, elliptical, apex broadly rounded, margins subparallel. Costal area narrow, opaque, margin slightly sinuate in middle. Apices as broad as base, rounded. Coloration of forewings green to greenish-yellow in light phase or brown in dark phase, with either phase having darker, longitudinal striations of base color throughout. Both color phases with a transverse, crescent-shaped to triangular, white marking merged into stigma, typically outlined in blackish-brown or reddish-brown. Darkened outline of white forewing maculation occasionally faded to absent. Ventral surface of forewings with white discoidal marking bleeding through, surrounding by large reddish-pink blotch. Stigma large, linear to slightly ovate, bright white and callous in both sexes. Male hindwings slightly longer than forewings with anal area pigmented brownish-black throughout, broken by hyaline cross-veins and a scattering of uneven, hyaline tessellation, becoming darker toward posterior margin. Discoidal area with reddish-brown margin, apices reddish-brown. Female hindwings with anal area hyaline to blackish throughout basal portion, becoming tessellated with opaque yellow in distal third. Major venation yellowish. Dark phase individuals may have anal area infumated with clear blotches throughout. Discoidal area and apices yellow to greenish-yellow.

Abdomen. Male abdomen slender, elongated, pigmented entirely reddish-orange; tergites I-V banded with black on distal third. Female abdomen fusiform with widest dilation at tergite V, pigmented yellowish green. Supra-anal plate very short, triangular with rounded apex, keeled, wider than long. Subgenital plate very large in male, slightly longer than wide. Cerci exceeding subgenital plate, cylindrical; styli very short.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 45-60; pronotum length 15-26; forewing length 28-39; prothoracic coxa 9-10; prothoracic femur length 10-13; metathoracic femur length 17.5-19. *Female.* Body length 43-76; pronotum length 18-33; forewing length 19-34.5; prothoracic femur length 13-16.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* are fairly robust, oval in shape. Distal end oblique, flattened; proximal end broadly rounded. Lateral surface ribbed, delimiting approximately 16-19 egg chambers. External wall golden brown in color with wide, slightly raised, whitish-tan emergence area consisting of 22-24 teardrop-shaped openings placed alternately down center of dorsal surface. These openings are sealed with dried froth until nymph emergence. *Oothecae* are attached along their entire ventral surface so that they sit with the dorsal surface exposed and thus the emergence area is parallel to the substrate. Oviposition sites include woody plant stems, thick twigs, and flattened surfaces of natural vegetation.

Development. Proto-nymphs molt embryonic cuticle after threading 1-3 mm past emergence flaps. First instar nymphs will then quickly disperse away from the ootheca and their siblings. Nymphs resemble adults in form and coloration, especially toward later instars. First instar nymphs are reddish-brown in color, gradually turning greenish or

brownish as they age. Younger instar nymphs range in color from green to brown, typically with darkened apices of meso/metathoracic femora and tibiae. Light phase individuals may have interior surface of forecoxae and forefemora largely yellow. Older instar nymphs demonstrate a wide array of green and brown mottling of pronotum, abdomen, and legs, especially during final instar. Wing buds of mature nymphs commonly tinted yellowish or striated with reddish-brown, thickly margined with yellowish-white, with prominent developing stigma. Abdomen marked with yellow band down median.

Adulthood. Adults of this species may be encountered year-round, often co-occurring with nymphs from overlapping generations. Adults of both sexes, as well as nymphs, are found on trunks of lemon and banana trees among flowering weeds, low bushes, and other vegetation within gardens, fields, and forest undergrowth.

Ethology. Adult males are attracted to lights at night and are, in general, much more active than females. Females may respond to threats with a deimatic display that involves facing the aggressor, unfurling both wings above body, partial abdominal dorsiflexion, and outward extension of forelegs.

References. Palisot (1805) pg 61; Burmeister (1838) pg 539; Guérin-Ménéville (1857) pg 348; de Haan (1842) pg 75; Saussure (1871) pgs 50-52; Saussure (1872) pgs 245-247; Stal (1877) pg 39; Cockerell (1894) pg 258; Westwood (1889) pg 36; Saussure & Zehntner (1894) pg 146; Rehn (1903) pg 131; Rehn (1904) pgs 564-565; Rehn (1911) pg 11; Giglio-Tos (1917) pgs 53-57; Giglio-Tos (1927) pg 383; Beier (1935) pg 94; Terra (1995) pg 70; Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert (2004) pgs 42-44; Shcherbakov (2018) pers. comm

Caribbean Distribution: The Bahamas, Cayman Islands, Cuba, Hispaniola, and Jamaica

To cite this article: Anderson, K. 2020. Revalidation of *Isomantis* Giglio-Tos, 1917. *Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research*. 1 (1): 1-8